

Increased selectivity for planar chromatography by ion exchange : Cation chromatography on papers impregnated with titanium(IV) based inorganic ion exchangers in DMSO-HNO₃ mobile phases

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Planar chromatography of thirty six metal ions on titanium(IV) phosphate, titanium(IV) tungstate and titanium(IV) molybdate impregnated papers in DMSO-HNO₃ mobile phases has been carried out. The ion-exchange capacity of papers is determined and the effects of solvent composition, impregnation and pH on R_F values are studied. For K^+ , Rb^+ and Cs^+ , $R_F = KC^{1/2}$, where C is the nitric acid concentration. The movement of ions is explained on the basis of ion-exchange, adsorption and precipitation. Alberti and Torracca's view for the prediction of elution sequence from R_F values has been checked. The sequence of adsorption of ions follows the order : titanium(IV) molybdate > titanium(IV) tungstate > titanium(IV) phosphate. Some of the analytically important separations are reported.

Few studies are reported on the chromatographic behaviour of metal ions on papers impregnated with titanium(IV) based inorganic ion-exchangers^{1,2}.

Dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) offers numerous advantages as an eluent in cation-exchange chromatography³. Chromatographic studies of toxic metal ions on silica gel-G with DMSO-HNO₃ and DMSO-HCl as mobile phases were reported earlier⁴. Recently, planar chromatography of metal ions on stannic selenite silicate layers in DMSO-HNO₃ mobile phases has been reported⁵. All these studies suffer from various limitations.

We have, therefore, decided to perform planar chromatography of a number of metal ions on titanium(IV) based inorganic ion-exchange papers using DMSO-HNO₃ mobile phase. HNO₃ was chosen because it is a non-complexing acid so that the understanding of equilibria is simplified.

Results and Discussion

The results of the plots of R_F versus solvent composition for DMSO-1 M HNO₃ mobile phases in varying ratios for all the metal ions on plain and impregnated papers, reveal that titanium(IV) tungstate papers are highly selective for Mo^{VI}, Se^{IV} and Bi^{III} titanium(IV) phosphate papers for W^{VI}, Se^{IV}, Mo^{VI}, Bi^{III}, Sb^{III}, Fe^{III}, Rb^I, K^I and Cs^I; and titanium(IV) molybdate papers specifically adsorb W^{VI}. It is further observed that in pure DMSO, R_F values for all the metal ions except Cd^{II}, Tl^I and Hg^{II} on titanium(IV) tungstate papers are low. The same is true for Cd^{II}, Tl^I Hg^{II} and Hg^{II} on titanium(IV) molybdate papers, and for Hg^{II}, Pb^{II}, Pd^{II}, Co^{II}, Ba^{II}, Sr^{II}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Ca^{II}, La^{III} and Ce^{III} on titanium(IV) phosphate papers. Further, for most of the metal ions studied, R_F values are higher in 1 M HNO₃ than in pure DMSO possibly because these ions have to

compete with H⁺ ions for exchange sites leading to a higher R_F in 1 M HNO₃ media.

The R_i values (R_F on plain papers - R_F on impregnated papers) for all the metal ions were calculated and found usually to be positive. In pure DMSO, the R_F of metal ions on plain papers is higher than that on impregnated ones, probably because (i) the metal ions are more strongly adsorbed on impregnated papers and (ii) impregnated papers have a higher cation exchange capacity than plain papers. On addition of HNO₃, the R_F values on plain and impregnated papers increase sharply because the metal ions must now compete with H⁺ ions for exchange sites.

For majority of metal ions, the R_F values are found to be lower for 70% (v/v) DMSO and higher for 30% (v/v) DMSO in the mobile phase. This is very much in agreement with earlier study⁶ for Mg^{II}. The distribution coefficient for Mg^{II} is maximum at 70% (v/v) DMSO and minimum at 30% (v/v) DMSO, showing that R_F values of metal ions are closely related to their distribution coefficients⁷.

The zero R_F for a number of metal ions on impregnated papers may be due to precipitation, ion-exchange and strong adsorption owing to high charge. On mixing solution of the metal ion with pure DMSO and DMSO-1 M HNO₃ (9 : 1), a precipitate was obtained for Zr^{IV}. The zero R_F for Zr^{IV} on plain papers is, therefore, due to the precipitation mechanism. On mixing with other DMSO-1 M HNO₃ mobile phases, none of the ion was precipitated. In order to simulate conditions on impregnated papers, the sodium salt of the anion was added to the metal ion solution followed by the mobile phase. A number of ions were precipitated under these conditions. Here also the precipitation mechanism holds good.

A very low R_F for Al^{III} in pure DMSO on all the three papers is probably due to the formation of a large complex⁸ such as $[Al(DMSO)]^{3+}$. The behaviour of Cr^{III} on all the impregnated papers is quite different from that of Mo^{VI} and W^{VI} , possibly because the properties of the first transition element along a group differ rather widely from those of the other elements in that group. In aqueous media, the R_F values for Fe^{III} is generally lower than that for Cu^{II} probably because Fe -DMSO complex $[Fe(DMSO)_6]^{3+}$ is larger than the one formed by Cu^{II} , i.e. $[Fe(DMSO)_4]^{2+}$ ⁹. Ce^{III} has a significant R_F values in all the mobile phases studied owing to the formation of soluble complexes in polar mobile phases¹⁰.

The behaviour of Ag^I is quite different. Usually it interacts with the ion-exchanger resulting in a very low or zero R_F for all mobile phases. It has been shown by Murray and Fuerstenau¹¹ that metal ions are preferably exchanged when the gel has a negative surface charge, but Ag^I is considerably exchanged even when the gel has a positive charge. This has been explained by the authors on the assumption that the adsorption of Ag^I is due to the Ag^I -matrix interaction. Contrary to it, Ag^I has a higher R_F on plain papers because it is highly polarisable and hence interacts strongly with DMSO. The Ag -DMSO complex interacts less plain paper resulting in a higher R_F . However, as soon as HNO_3 is added both H^+ and Ag^I ions compete for DMSO and since DMSO interacts more strongly with H^+ ions, the R_F suddenly falls.

It is interesting to compare the R_F values of metal ions on papers impregnated with titanium(IV) molybdate, titanium(IV) tungstate and titanium(IV) phosphate in pure DMSO and in DMSO-1M HNO_3 as mobile phase. The results

Fig. 1. Plots of R_F vs C for Cs^+ in DMSO- HNO_3 and butanol- HNO_3 mobile phases. (■) DMSO-8 M HNO_3 , (x) DMSO-1 M HNO_3 and (●) butanol-8 M HNO_3

reveal that in pure DMSO, the R_F values in general follow the order : titanium(IV) phosphate > titanium(IV) tungstate > titanium(IV) molybdate. This may be due to the fact that the phosphate papers are slightly less ionised than the tungstate papers which in turn are less ionised than molybdate ones. The pk_2 for phosphoric acid (as sodium dihydrogen phosphate) is 7.2 and pk_1 for tungstic acid and molybdic acid are 4.2 and 2.54, respectively. It is supported by the fact that the difference in R_F of most of the metal ions on these papers diminishes if we compare the chromatographic behaviour in DMSO-1 M HNO_3 (1 : 1). The only exceptions are those ions which have very low R_F values, probably because they interact chemically with the paper matrix

Fig. 2. Plots of R_F vs \sqrt{C} for K^+ , Rb^+ and Cs^+ in DMSO-1 M HNO_3 system

We showed earlier¹² that using butanol-8 M HNO_3 in varying ratios, the R_F values for majority of metal ions on titanium(IV) tungstate papers could be represented by a simple equation, $R_F = a + bC^2$, C being the nitric acid concentration. We did not study higher ratios of HNO_3 as the mixture is liable to explode. It was observed that for K^+ , Rb^+ and Cs^+ ions $a = 0$ and R_F vs C^2 plots are straight-lines passing through the origin. If we replace butanol with DMSO, the dielectric constant becomes so high that even in DMSO-8 M HNO_3 (9 : 1), the R_F values for these ions are greater than 0.7 (Fig. 1). It was, therefore, decided to chose DMSO-1 M HNO_3 in which even higher proportions of HNO_3 could be used without the fear of explosion. In this case, we again found that a very simple equation holds good for K^+ , Rb^+ and Cs^+ , $R_F = KC^{1/2}$. The plots of R_F vs \sqrt{C} are straight-lines (Fig. 2). It is interesting to note that in butanol-8 M HNO_3 mobile phases, the R_F first increases slightly with HNO_3 concentration and then rapidly, while in DMSO-1 M HNO_3 mobile phases, a sharp increase is observed (Fig. 1). This difference can be explained by measuring the dielectric constant by oscillometric studies. However, it could not be possible as the conductivity of the solutions was too high.

It is well known that the pH of a non-aqueous media gives a rough measure of the H^+ ion concentrations¹³. As usual we expected that for the same HNO_3 concentrations, the pH in DMSO will be lower than in butanol, but the values for both these mobile phases (in the ratio 9 : 1) are 1.35 and 0.10, respectively. This can be explained by the fact that DMSO interacts strongly with H^+ ions, therefore, the pH is higher in DMSO than in butanol media. However, DMSO on interaction with H^+ ion gives rise to positive ions and their net concentration is greater in DMSO than in butanol. Since these ions compete with alkali metals for exchange sites, the R_F values in DMSO are greater than in butanol media. Thus the R_F for these ions show greater increase initially in DMSO-1 M HNO_3 mobile phases than in butanol- 8 M HNO_3 ones.

It is interesting that both these cases can be expressed by the general equation, $R_F = KC^{1/n}$, the Freundlich adsorption isotherm. The relation is useful since for the alkali metal ions, the R_F on plain and impregnated papers are almost the same and therefore the same equation holds good. In case of butanol-8 M HNO_3 mobile phases, the exponent of C is 2 and for DMSO-1 M HNO_3 mobile phases it is 1/2. This difference is probably related to the dielectric constant of the media. The KC^2 curve for stannic arsenate papers fits a large number of metal ions but the $KC^{1/2}$ curve fits only for K^+ , Rb^+ and Cs^+ because DMSO is a complexing agent and interacts with most of the metal ions thereby limiting the application of this equation to other ions.

On the basis of R_F values, a large number of binary and ternary separations are possible. Some of the important ones actually achieved are as follows : (a) Ba^{II} - Sr^{II} ; Zn^{II} or Ni^{II} - Co^{II} or Pd^{II} ; Zr^{IV} - Th^{IV} ; Sb^{III} - Bi^{III} - Pd^{II} ; Mn^{II} - Zn^{II} or Cr^{III} ; Nd^{III} or Sm^{III} - Pr^{III} , Ag^I - Pb^{II} - Cu^{II} , Fe^{III} - Fe^{II} ; UO_2^{II} - VO^{II} ; Ce^{IV} - Ce^{III} on titanium(IV) phosphate papers, (b) Zr^{IV} - Th^{IV} ; Mo^{VI} - Cr^{III} ; and Ag^I - Cu^{II} - Hg^{II} on titanium(IV) tungstate papers, and (c) Zn^{II} - Cd^{II} - Hg^{II} ; Sb^{III} - Bi^{III} - Pb^{II} or Cu^{II} or Cd^{II} ; Zr^{IV} - Th^{IV} ; Se^{IV} - W^{VI} and Cr^{III} - Zn^{II} on titanium(IV) molybdate papers.

Experimental

Chromatography was performed on Whatman No. 1 paper strips (25 × 3.5 cm) glass jars.

Titanium(IV) chloride (Reidel) was used. All other chemical and solvents were of AnalaR grade.

Papers impregnated with titanium(IV) based inorganic ion exchangers were prepared in the same manner as the titanium(IV) molybdate impregnated papers reported earlier². For Na^+ ion (Na^+ - H^+ exchange), the exchange capacity (in mequiv/g) of treated papers was determined by column experiments (Saturation method¹⁴) and the values are as follows : Ti^{IV} -phosphate, 0.34; Ti^{IV} -tungstate, 0.35; Ti^{IV} -molybdate, 0.33.

The test solutions were generally 0.1 M in the metal nitrate or chloride and were prepared as described earlier¹⁵. Conventional spot test reagents were used for detection purpose.

Procedure : Test solution (0.02 ml) containing 2×10^{-6} moles of the ion under study was placed with a thin glass capillary. The paper was then conditioned for 10 min, developed in the mobile phase until the ascent was 11 cm and the R_F value was calculated.

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